

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF FINANCIAL ENTERPRISE MANAGEMENT

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It is shown how to effectively manage finances at the enterprise, and groups of financial resources are allocated for this. A model of financial management has been developed, which allows to interconnect internal and external management of financial resources.

The main goal of an industrial enterprise at present is not only making a profit, but also creating a competitive business that can adequately respond to market demand. At the same time, being an economic entity in the real sector of the economy, an industrial enterprise must, in order to achieve the goal, progressively and flexibly manage finances, process attracted resources into final products to meet the needs of consumers to the maximum. Finance is the science of managing cash flows.

Consequently, the financial policy of the enterprise is aimed at mobilizing financial resources, their use and, if necessary, redistribution to achieve the goal of both the enterprise as a whole and the individual employee.

Effective implementation of financial management aimed at increasing competitiveness and maximizing business profitability is possible if there is an operational financial model for managing the enterprise. This model should provide controllability of financial resource flows, income and expenses, the possibility of obtaining a current assessment of the performance of the enterprise, as well as its structural divisions.

Two groups of resource objects can be distinguished in management.

The financial resources of the enterprise itself:

- income from sales;
- entrepreneurial capital;
- depreciation deductions;
- profit.

Financial resources that an enterprise can use from outside:

- budget receipts;
- investments;
- income from financial investments;
- insurance compensations;
- funds received in the stock market;
- borrowed funds.

In the conditions of the modern economy, the management of financial resources, that is, the elements of cash costs necessary for the implementation of business operations of the enterprise, is implemented through a financial mechanism.

Intra-production monetary relations that make up the content of an enterprise's finances can be combined into relatively homogeneous groups. With the participation of the finances of the enterprise, a competitive product is created and distributed to the markets.

Financial management of any enterprise is one of the main elements of general management. In corporate structures, the role of financial management increases, since in this case, in addition to managing the finances of individual enterprises, it is necessary to manage the consolidated financial flows of the entire group as a whole.

In a market economy, effective management involves optimizing the resource potential of an enterprise. In this situation, the importance of effective management of financial resources sharply increases. The financial well-being of the enterprise as a whole, its owners and employees depends on how effectively and expediently they are transformed into fixed and working capital, as well as into means of stimulating the workforce. Under these conditions, financial resources are of paramount importance, since this is the only type of enterprise resources that can be directly transformed into any other type of resources with a minimum time lag. To some extent, the role of financial resources is important at all levels of management (strategic, tactical, operational), but it is of particular importance in terms of the enterprise development strategy. Thus, financial management, as one of the main functions of the management apparatus, acquires a key role in a market economy.

The relevance of the principles laid down in the system of financial calculation, its practical application in creating competitiveness makes it possible to eliminate the internal contradictions of the enterprise.

One of the main contradictions is the inconsistency of the chain of operational management: planning - accounting - analysis. Planning in a market economy should be based on statistical methods of market research.

All of the above allows us to conclude that financial management of an enterprise is a process aimed at optimizing the movement and distribution of funds to achieve the goal of both the enterprise as a whole and individual employees. Financial management is aimed at solving the problem of influencing the level and structure of cash flows in such a way that the enterprise achieves

its goal. Essentially, financial management is the management of monetary resources.

At the same time, the priority role should be given to natural indicators of demand in the market. The main estimated indicator of the activity of an industrial enterprise is the volume of output, and not economic stability and market share. In this regard, the problem of incompatibility of operational planned and accounting indicators of the financial activity of the enterprise arose.

However, an approach is needed to study the financial management of enterprises, since they form the economy of various industries. Financial management should be carried out in any enterprise. Financial management is carried out through financial analysis, planning, accounting, control and regulation of funds. The financial management system should be self-developing. This reflects the emergence of such qualities as flexibility and adaptability to change, focus on innovation, search and development of ideas to attract investment. The financial management system in the new conditions becomes a source of additional financial resources for business development.

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